

ESO Data Reduction and Archive

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The end-to-end operation model

Usage of data reduction tools

Observatory

- Quality control at telescope and at ESO headquarter
- Processing of pre-imaging data
- Production and certification of master calibration frames
- Production of science data products for the archive facility.

Community

- Data reduction with custom settings of parameters
- Inspect intermediate products
- Insert customized steps into pipeline processing

ESO Data Reduction Infrastructure

ESO Internal only	Public	communalities
Data organization		
DO at telescope, ABbuilder QC Garching	CalSelector service, Gasgano, Reflex DO	OCA language
Algorithms		
Quick look recipes	CPL pipeline recipes, Reflex Python plotting, (Molecfite and other tools)	CPL
Data Reduction workflows		
Paranal & QC cascades, Phoenix	Reflex	Esorex recipe execution

Data Organization

Organise files into data sets = all files needed to reduce one set of science files.

Data Organisation

- Pipeline (ESO Observatory, Data Organiser)
 - On-the-fly data processing (event driven)
 - Template-based processing
 - Static calibration database (only certified products are used)
- Quality Control (ESO Headquarters, ABbuilder)
 - Batch processing of complete data sets (all science and calibration data produced by one ESO instrument in one night)
 - Best available calibrations are used => data must be organized according to the **Calibration Cascade**
- Science Archive (CalSelector)
 - Web-based association of calibration data in archive (raw and reduced) to science data
- Data Reduction by Community (Reflex, Gasgano)
 - Data organisation of files on disk for different processing cascades.

OCA Rules

- Data organisation defined as text files “OCA rules”
- Three types of rules:
 - Classification („This is a **Raw Dark**“)

```
if DPR.CATG=="CALIB" and DPR.TYPE=="DARK" then
{
RAW.TYPE = "DARK";
}
```

- Organization („These Raw Darks are processed together”)

```
select execute(MAKEDARK) from inputFiles
where RAW.TYPE=="DARK" group by TPL.START
```

- Association (“select Biases based on properties of Raw Darks“ or “process these Raw Darks together using selected Biases“)

```
action MAKEDARK
{
select file as MASTER_BIAS from calibFiles where
PRO.CATG=="MASTER_BIAS" and inputFile.DET.WIN1.BINX==DET.WIN1.BINX;
}
```


CPL Pipelines

- Consortia are required to deliver pipeline recipes coded in C using the “ESO Common Pipeline Library” and “High

Instrument	Release Notes	Package	User Manual	Cookbook	Additional Documents	Additional Datasets	EsoReflex	Status
AMBER	2015-03-06	4.3.3	4.3.2					Operational on hold
CRIRES	2015-08-04	2.3.3	1.13	Cookbook				Operational on hold
EFOSC	2015-07-10	2.2.4	1.0			Demo Data		End of maintenance
FORS	2015-09-18	5.1.4	5.2			Demo Data (29 MB)	Tutorial: 1.0 (FORS-IMG) Tutorial: 1.0 (FORS-PMOS) Tutorial: 1.9 (FORS-SPEC) Demo Data: 0.8	Active
GIRAFFE	2015-11-02	2.14.2	2.14.2	Cookbook		Standard Calibration Files page		Operational on hold
HAWKI	2015-04-20	1.8.18	1.11			Demonstration Package (2.5 GB)		Operational on hold
ISAAC	2015-04-17	6.1.5	1.4			Static Calibration Files (50 MB)		End of maintenance
KMOS	2016-01-22	1.3.17	2.17				Tutorial: 1.6 Demo Data: 1.2	Active
MIDI	2015-04-15	2.8.4	2.8.3					End of maintenance
MUSE	2015-10-06	1.2.1	1.2.1			MUSE IFU 6 trace tables Legacy MUSE static calibrations	Tutorial: 7.0 Demo Data: 1.3	Active
NACO	2015-06-01	4.4.1	1.1					Operational on hold
SINFONI	2015-10-26	2.7.0	19.5		ADA IV 2006 paper	Calibration Database Example (255 MB) Demonstration Package (1.2 GB)	Tutorial: 1.5 Demo Data: 0.2	Operational on hold
SOFI	2015-04-17	1.5.6	1.2					End of maintenance
SPHERE	2015-03-10	0.15.0						Active
UVES	2015-09-14	5.5.7	22.11 (UVES) 18.5 (UVES-FIBRE)			Demonstration Package (2.0 GB)	Tutorial: 6.6 (UVES) Tutorial: 1.5 (UVES-FIBRE) Demo Data: 4.4	Operational on hold
VIMOS	2015-10-05	3.0.6	7.0			Demonstration Package (1.7 GB)	Tutorial: 2.3 (VIMOS-IFU) Tutorial: 2.0 (VIMOS-MOS) Demo Data: 0.4	Active
VISIR	2016-02-25	4.1.7	1.5				Demo Data: 0.1	Operational on hold
XSHOOTER	2015-09-14	2.6.8	12.7			Additional NIR telluric model catalog (190 MB)	Tutorial: 2.6 Demo Data: 1.2	Operational on hold

- Scientific oversight by Garching instrument project scientists during development, Science Data Products Group and Paranal instrument scientist during operation

High level Data Reduction Library HDRL

A. Gabasch

- Overscan computation and subtraction
- Master frame combination(Bias/Dark/Flat)
- Cosmic ray detection on a single image
- Bad pixel determination on
 - Single images.
 - Stacks of identical images, e.g. bias/dark frames.
 - Sequence of images, e.g. domeflats with different exposure time.
- Computation of the Strehl ratio
- Fringe detection and removal
- Source detection/extraction

More to come:

- Optimal Extraction
- Wavelength calibration
- Detection of pick-up noise
- ...

KMOS: combining reconstructed cubes

Representative spectra of individual datacubes that are combined for the selected object. The user can (de)select the exposures from final combination

List of combined datacubes for each object

Representative spectrum and image of the selected object (from final combined cube)

The screenshot shows the 'kmos_combine_interactive' software interface. It features a 'Files Selection' panel with a list of files (e.g., 'combine_sci_reconstructed_001.fits') and a 'Recipe Parameters' panel on the right. The main display area contains a 'Spectrum' plot (blue and red lines), a 'Collapsed image' (grayscale), and a 'IFUs (skipped in black)' plot showing multiple spectra stacked vertically. A legend at the bottom explains the symbols used in the file selection list.

Files Selection (double-click Left Mouse Button)

- combine_sci_reconstructed_001.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_002.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_003.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_004.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_007.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_010.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_014.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_018.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_020.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_021.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_027.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_029.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_030.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_048.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_058.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_069.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_100.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_101.fits
- combine_sci_reconstructed_103.fits

Recipe Parameters

Comb. Other

name: [text box]

fmethod: gauss

flux:

edge_nan:

cmethod: ksigma

cpos_rej: 3

Continue Wkf

Re-run Recipe

Help

Disable this window in subsequent runs

Use the parameters above as initial values in subsequent executions of this recipe

This data belongs to dataset: KMOS.2013-06-30T23:48:06.049_tpl

Files Info

View Selection (Left Mouse Button)

- Display input and output spectra
- Display output spectra
- Display input spectra

Data Reduction Workflows

- Even when algorithms (recipes) are given, data reduction involves many decisions:
 - Which data do I process first?
 - Which files are processed by which recipes?
 - Which files need to be re-processed?
 - How do I organize the output?
- **Workflow** differs for different use cases. Example:
 - QC0 use static calibration
 - QC1 processes all calibrations independent of later use
 - Desktop reduction processes all data for given datasets

Scientific Workflow Systems

- System to define and execute series of data manipulation steps
- Flexible intuitive workflow essential for desktop data reduction
- **Reflex** uses Kepler <https://kepler-project.org>
- Kepler provides the graphical user interface
- **Reflex** is a collection of Kepler components (“actors”) that allow to execute ESO recipes, data display GUIs, and Python scripts
- Available for Linux and OS X

Workflow Instructions

To run this workflow on the demo data:

- Turn on highlighting. Choose "Tools"-> "Animate at Runtime" from top menu and set it to "1".
- Press the "Run" button OR cntrl-R to start the workflow.

To run on a different data set:

- Click on ROOT_DATA_DIR and set as appropriate. All subdirectories of RAWDATA_DIR will be searched for data.
- If desired, change END_PRODUCTS_DIR.
- Press the "Run" button OR cntrl-R to start the workflow.

To monitor the progress of the workflow in more detail:

- Open "Window" -> "Runtime Window" in top menu before starting the workflow.

Setup Directories

Input:

- ROOT_DATA_DIR: /sdp_test_data/mneaser/UK/assess_hawki_1_1/A1689
- RAWDATA_DIR: \$ROOT_DATA_DIR/RAW
- CALIB_DATA_DIR: /sdp_test_data/mneaser/Reflex_workflows/Reflex_hawki_vimo...

- TWOMASS_CATALOGUE_DIR: /sdp_test_data/CASU_2MASS
- PPMXL_CATALOGUE_DIR: /sdp_test_data/CASU_PPMXL
- LOCAL_CATALOGUE_DIR:

Working Directories:

- BOOKKEEPING_DIR: \$ROOT_DATA_DIR/reflex_book_keeping/hawki
- LOGS_DIR: \$ROOT_DATA_DIR/reflex_logs/hawki
- TMP_PRODUCTS_DIR: \$ROOT_DATA_DIR/reflex_tmp_products/hawki

Output:

- END_PRODUCTS_DIR: \$ROOT_DATA_DIR/reflex_end_products

Global Parameters

= actor with interactive option

- RecipeFailureMode: Ask Global parameter for the behaviour when a recipe fails. 'Ask': choice to continue or stop will be presented 'Continue': workflow will ignore errors and continue 'Stop': workflow will stop.
- EraseDirs: false 'true': BOOKKEEPING_DIR, TMP_PRODUCTS_DIR and LOGS_DIR directories erased at start of workflow; Lazy mode will not work
- FITS_VIEWER: fv name of local fits viewer/editor application to inspect files
- GlobalPlotInteractivity: true Turn on/off interactive GUIs for all subworkflows NB: Enable_Interactivity inside subworkflows have precedence
- ProvenanceExplorerEnabled: true
- SelectDatasetMethod: interactive
- Compute readgain table: false true: computed the readgain table from raw frames in the dataset. false: uses the readgain table from static calibrations. Default: false.

Catalogue Selection

Select catalogues (on local machine and/or for CDS search). Input values must be within the allowed ranges; at least one photometric and one astrometric valid catalogues must be provided (either from local machine or for CDS search). If these criteria are not fulfilled, the workflow will stop. No check is done beforehand.

- ASTROM_CATALOGUE: 1 Select catalogues on local machine
- CDS ASTROMETRIC CATALOGUE: wise CDS astrometric catalogue, <none | 2mass | usnob | ppmxl | wise>
- PHOTOM_CATALOGUE: 0 0: 2MASS; 1: PPMXL; 2: LOCAL
- CDS PHOTOMETRIC CATALOGUE: 2mass CDS photometric catalogue, <none | 2mass | ppmxl | wise>

Step 1: Data Organisation and Selection

Step 2: Creation of Master Calibration Files

Step 3: Standard Star and Science Images Reduction

Step 4: Output Organisation

KMOS WORKFLOW

Global parameters for data reduction

● global_pix_scale: 0.2

Spatial resolution in arcsec/pixel used during datacube reconstruction in the recipes kmos_illumination and kmos_sci_red. Default = 0.2

● UseSkyFlats?: no

Specify the strategy for illumination correction. If set to yes, the twilight sky flats will be used if present. If set to yes but no sky flats are present in the dataset, the illumination correction is not done. If set to no, the internal lamp flats are used for illumination correction. Default value: yes.

● telluric and response correction: 0

Specify the response and telluric correction to use. Default=0. Valid entries:

0: Response, telluric correction, and zeropoint evaluated from standard star or user provided file (category: TELLURIC). User provided file has priority. If none are present, the average response curve and zeropoint from static calibration is applied if present, otherwise products are not flux calibrated.

1: Apply only telluric correction and zeropoint from user-provided file (category TELLURIC_CORR).

2: Apply only response correction from static calibration (category: RESPONSE). Zeropoint is computed either from standard star or from user-provided file (category: TELLURIC). This option is recommended when correcting for telluric absorption with external tools (e.g., molecfit).

3: Apply response correction from static calibration (category: RESPONSE) and telluric correction from user provided file (category: TELLURIC_CORR). Zeropoint from user-provided file is used.

Global parameters that allows to define:

- The illumination correction strategy: twilight flats or lamp flats.
- The Telluric correction and response curve correction strategy:
 - Response and telluric correction from pipeline (using observed standard star)
 - Merge the static Response calibration with an user-provided telluric correction (obtained, e.g., using molecfit).
 - Response correction only (from static calibration).
 - Telluric correction only (from user-provided calibration)

MUSE-ZAP workflow

Step 1:
Data Organisation
and Selection

Step 2:
Creation of Sky Mask

Step 3:
Removing residual sky lines
from datacube

Step 4:
Output Organisation

Sky residuals are decomposed into principal components either using:

- Sky regions around the target;
- Dedicated sky observations (if present in the dataset).

min_frac and max_frac specify the fraction of the field of view image to consider as sky. Defaults min_frac = 0.05; max_frac = 0.15 indicate that the fractions between 5% and 15% of faintest pixels are considered as sky.

- min_frac: 0.05
- max_frac: 0.15

Main ZAP parameters (the full parameter list is inside the ZAP actor)

- Eigenspectra_detection_type (optimizeType): 'normal'
- Percentage of eigenspectra (pevals): 1
- Number of eigenspectra (npevals): 30
- median_filter(fwidthSVD): 500
- median_filter(fwidthSPI): 30
- External Sky components (full path): 'none'

Optimization method to compute the number of eigenspectra used for each segment: 'none', 'normal', 'enhanced'. If 'none', the percentage of eigenspectra must be specified with pevals. pevals can be either a single value that will be used for all of the segments. If pevals is negative or zero, the number of eigenspectra is used (npevals). Note that 'normal' or 'enhanced' methods use more memory. In case of memory issues, it is suggested to set it to 'none'. Default 'normal'.

Window size for the continuum filter, for the SVD computation.

Window size for the continuum filter used to remove the continuum features for calculating the eigenvalues per spectrum. Smaller values better trace the sources

Path of an input FITS file containing a Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) computed on empty sky datacube. SVD characterizes the eigenvalues of the eigenspectra the sky residuals are decomposed into. If set to 'none' computes SVD on the sky mask regions (of the object or sky cube, depending on the content of the dataset). If specified, it overrides any SVD computed by the workflow.

Interactive window to design the sky-mask.

- It uses the Python code by Soto et al. ([2016MNRAS.458.3210S](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw2108))
- It is independent of the muse pipeline.

Science Archive

- The **ESO Science Archive Facility** (SAF) is the operational and technical data archive of the La Silla Paranal Observatory and a science resource in its own right
 - It is the one access point to La Silla Paranal data
- Data holdings (**raw data and data products**)
 - ~700 TB of data in ~40 million files and ~30 billion database rows worth of header keywords
 - Storage technology is not a concern, database management more challenging
 - Inflow: ~12 TB/month; outflow ~15 TB/month

Data products in the SAF

Two channels to feed the archive with data products:

- **Internal:** automated processing with scientifically validated pipelines
 - UVES echelle, X-Shooter echelle, HARPS echelle, FLAMES-MEDUSA, MUSE, then HAWK-I and VIMOS IMG, KMOS, ...
 - Migration of legacy historical Advanced Data Products completed
- **External:** Principal Investigators of Public Surveys, Large Programmes, ... provide high-level products (mosaics, source catalogues, ...) that we validate and integrate

Arnaboldi et al: Summary in December 2013 Messenger: papers from ESO, the Survey Teams and archive user

Polling the community: ESO2020 questionnaire

- “How important is access to the following sorts of archived data products in order to maximize your scientific productivity?”
 - Statistically (very) significant sample: 1439 answers

— Somewhat important to Essential — Essential or Very important

Number of archive data categories considered “Somewhat important” to “Essential”

Archive access to data: building a community

Romaniello et al, The Messenger, March 2016

Both pipeline products and data from the community

- Archive users
- The number of PI/Cols of Public Surveys

processed data from

the number of

Availability of products didn't decrease access to the corresponding raw data

The science return of the SAF

- Archive refereed papers
 - ~25% of ESO's output
 - ~5% of La Silla Paranal data only published as archive papers

telbib.eso.org

Archive services: status quo

- **The problem:** as a user, how do I find my way among 40 million files described by 30 billion keywords?
 - Classical form based interface
 - Selection of calibration data (raw or processed)
- The science potential of ESO's Science Archive Facility is limited by its limited search capabilities
 - The user-SAF interaction is static and offers limited data discovery capabilities
 - Queries are expressed in terms of technical, rather than physical properties
 - E.g. Technical names of optical components in the light path vs. wavelength coverage and resolution
- Especially true as its content in terms of ready-for-science data products grows more and more

Archive services: evolution

- **Guiding principle:** establish a dialogue between the archive researchers, who know their science cases, and the archive, which knows its content
- First release concentrates on data products, including ALMA
 - Most immediate scientific return, metadata intrinsically more homogeneous, thanks to VO-inspired data standard
- Complex queries on science keywords that describe the physical properties of the data
 - Signal-to-noise ratio, wavelength coverage and resolution, limiting magnitude, ...
- Added-value services: visualization, facets, ...
- Programmatic access and interoperability

Some Ongoing Projects

- Data Organization
 - Upgrade of OCA.
 - Will allow more flexible design of pipeline recipes
 - Support for more complex conditions
- Pipelines
 - Support for new instruments
 - Use Molecfit in pipelines (KMOS)
 - Additions to HDRL to increase communalities among pipelines
- ESO Archive Facility
 - Expand holding of reduced data to new instruments: Hawk-I, VIMOS imaging, KMOS
 - Interface

Summary

- ESO supports data reductions for 3 different use cases:
 - Operations, quality control
 - Archive
 - Community
- Different use cases use different strategies and tools for
 - Data organization
 - Reduction workflow
- Different use cases use a common underlying infrastructure
 - Pipeline recipes
 - OCA data organisation